

Life history and plant host range of the rice green semilooper

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We used a greenhouse mass-rearing technique to study the life history of the rice green semilooper *Naranga aenescens* Moore. Development from egg to adult takes 18-21 d. Eggs are laid either singly or in clusters of 2-13 and hatch in 3-4 d. Larvae undergo 5 instars over 12-13 d, pupation takes 3-4 d, and adult moths live 5-6 d.

Of the 19 plant species tested, *Leersia hexandra* and *Echinochloa indica* were equally suitable to rice as hosts, but more eggs were laid on rice in a no-choice test (see table). Complete egg-to-adult development but low survival occurred on *Cyperus diffusus*, *Paspalum conjugatum*, *Paspalum paspalodes*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Echinochloa colona*, and sorghum. Larvae died during the first and second stadia in *Cyperus diffusus*, *Echinochloa*

Comparison of 16 weed and 3 crop species as *Naranga aenescens* host.^a

Plant species	Eggs laid ^b (no./female)	Larval development (d)	Pupal development (d)	Egg-to-adult survival (%)
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (rice)	454 a	14 a	4.3 ab	44 a
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	66 bcde	13 a	4.3 ab	56 a
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	22 de	13 a	6.3 bc	36 a
<i>Paspalum paspalodes</i>	121 bc	19 a	3.3 a	5 b
<i>Cyperus diffusus</i>	112 bc	26 b	4.7 abc	3 b
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> (sorghum)	60 bcd	15 a	11.7 d	7 b
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i>	36 bcde	26 b	6.7 c	3 b
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	97 bc	25 ^c	5.0 ^d	1 b
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	14 ef	15 ^c	5.0 ^d	5 b
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	161 ab	^e		
<i>Rottboellia exaltata</i>	140 bc	^e		
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	136 abc	^e		
<i>Paspalidium flavidum</i>	82 bcd	^e		
<i>Panicum repens</i>	53 bcde	^e		
<i>Zea mays</i> (maize)	52 bcde	^e		
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	45 de	^e		
<i>Commelina diffusa</i>	30 cde	^e		
<i>Fimbristylis littoralis</i>	9 fg	^e		
<i>Cyperus diffusus</i>	2 g	^e		

^aVegetative-stage plants were used. Av of 3 replications, 1 moth pair/cage (replication). In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($P = 0.05$). ^bNo-choice test as one plant species/cage. ^cLarval development attained in one replication only; not included in statistical analysis. ^dPupal development obtained only in one out of 3 replications; not included in statistical analysis. ^eLarvae died during first instar.

glabrescens, *Fimbristylis littoralis*, *Panicum repens*, *Rottboellia exaltata*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Commelina diffusa*,

Paspalidium flavidum, *Cyperus rotundus*, and maize. □

Influence of weather on populations of rice white leafhopper in light traps

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A modified Robinson's light trap with a 125-W mercury vapor lamp was used to trap white leafhopper (WL) *Cofana spectra* (Distant) at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, for 15 mo. Daily number of trapped WL was recorded as well as maximum and minimum temperature, relative humidity, and total rainfall. There was a highly significant negative

Association between light trap population of *C. spectra* and minimum temperature and rainfall. Light trap population represents total adults trapped in 4 wk.

Table 1. Relation between light trap catches of *C. spectra* and weather factors.

Weather factor	r value ^a
Max temp	-0.179
Min temp	-0.628**
Relative humidity	-0.147
Total rainfall	-0.270*

^a*Significant at 5% level, **significant at 1% level.

Table 2. Partial regression coefficients, standard error and proportional contribution of weather factors to regression of light trap population of *C. spectra*.

Weather factor	Partial regression coefficient	Standard error	Proportional contribution to R^2 (%)
Max temp	-7.816	6.468	2.42
Min temp	-26.365**	4.960	36.16
Relative humidity	-4.558	3.183	2.34
Total rainfall	-0.575	0.560	3.17

Constant term 'a' = 1305.255, $R^2 = 0.4411$. **Significant at 1% level.